

SZ-SB-III-01-03 Networking between parents from different schools (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851233
ID	SZ-Sb-III-01-03
Title	Networking between parents from different schools
Educational area	#school
Persona	P: Alvin - Legal guardian https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
Short description	Alvin seeks exchange with other parents whose children have special educational needs.
Result	Alvin connects with parents on BIRD whose children also have special educational needs.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Parent Gets Informed"• Part 2:"Parent Connects with Parent from Another School"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Alvin is registered at BIRD• Alvin is logged in to BIRD
Components	#buddyfinder #chat #learningpathfinder
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Due to a job change, Alvin Weierbach and his family are moving from Brandenburg to Bavaria. The move is imminent. While he and his wife will soon have to settle into their new jobs, their two daughters face the challenge of changing schools and adjusting to the new environment.

Lena, the younger of their two daughters, was recently diagnosed with special educational needs. Alvin wants to ensure that Lena receives the necessary support in her new environment and is therefore seeking information in advance.

Problem definition

In addition to finding the right school for his daughter Lena, Alvin is also looking for support, including establishing contact with other parents in Bavaria whose children have special educational needs. He hopes to learn more about their experiences and the options available for Lena, thus enabling her transition to be as smooth as possible.

Background and context

Lena has always had difficulties in school. The move to Bavaria brings new challenges, as Lena has to find her way around a new school system and with new teachers. Alvin is worried about all these changes. He is unfamiliar with the school system and the requirements in Bavaria. Furthermore, the situation is still new for him, and he has to figure out what it actually means for Lena to have special educational needs, what services are available at schools in Bavaria, and whether or how they need to apply for them.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Alvin needs a lot of information at once: In addition to his new job, he has to secure Lena's and Lisa's school registration and deal with the issue of special educational needs. This topic requires caution and discretion Lena shouldn't be disadvantaged at the new school as a result. Being able to clarify all of this in advance is a high priority for him.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Alvin has visited many different internet forums where affected parents gather to discuss their issues. The topic is extensive, and although Alvin has a lot of information, he hasn't been able to find suitable answers to his specific questions. Furthermore, these forums seem anonymous, and he would prefer to talk to someone directly rather than reading through long threads and articles that only raise more questions.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Parent Gets Informed"

Step 1: Alvin Weierbach opens the LearningPathFinder and searches for "parent exchange special educational needs".

Step 2: The following information and advice on special educational needs are recommended:

- School Office
- Advice Centers
- Online Portals

- Parent Initiatives and Self-Help Groups

Step 3: Alvin initially decides to connect with other parents, hoping to find answers to his questions in personal conversations. He is referred to the Buddy Finder and is redirected to it directly.

Part 2:"Parent Connects with Parent from Another School"

Step 1: Alvin updates his Buddyfinder profile by entering his move to Bavaria.

Step 2: After updating his data, the Buddyfinder will ask him again whether he agrees to share his data on BIRD for matching purposes. Alvin confirms this by clicking "Agree."

Step 3: Now he fills out the Buddyfinder search as follows:

- state: Bavaria
- City: Ebersberg (radius +50km)
- Keywords: special educational needs, high school
- Exchange with other parents
- Connect

Step 4: The Buddy Finder suggests parents with a similar profile to Alvin. Many of them live in Bavaria, even close to his new place of residence, and have children with special educational needs.

Step 5: Alvin decides to get in touch with one of the suggested parents, as he considers a one-to-one exchange to be more sensible at the beginning.

Step 6: He sends a contact request via Buddy Finder to father XY.

Step 7: Father XY receives the request by being notified by BIRD and accepts it.

Step 8: Alvin, in turn, receives a notification that his contact request has been accepted. He can now contact his buddy via chat.

Step 9: Alvin and father XY start exchanging ideas via chat.